

EXTRACTING WORDS' POLARITY WITH DEFINITION AND EXAMPLES

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Abstract- Text analytics are not only the need of readers but are also helpful for the researchers of opinion mining. During reading there are a lot of words which are not understandable for the readers, so the readers require a dictionary then. Finding a particular word in a dictionary takes quite some time, and the reader may very well be distracted. So there is a need of such analytics that user can find out definitions, examples on the spot. The authors propose a work which can not only save the readers' time, but also provides a way through which the readers will not lose their attention. This work also provides the lists of classified words with respect to positive, negative, objective and neutral polarities which are very helpful for opinion mining. After experimental results using WordNet dictionary, 75% definitions & 44% examples of user reviews, 92% definitions & 65% examples of politics domain, 92% definitions & 58% examples of sports domain and 87% definitions & 52% examples of medicine domain have been extracted.

1. INTRODUCTION

For the first time in human history, there is a huge amount of opinionated data in digital form coming from reviews, forum discussions, blogs, microblogs, Twitter, and social networks [1]. Opinion may be either direct or indirect. Most of the researchers are working on direct opinions. Instead of taking direct opinion, first it is important to check out that whether the given comments are opinion or not. Opinion extraction also requires a lot of effort as text data is in unstructured form [2] [3]. Learning based anaphora techniques have been used for opinion extraction and summarization [4] [5]. These opinions may be further furnished through regular [6] or comparative classification [7]. Regular classification is either subjective or objective opinion,[8], objective opinion means features from products' company and subjective opinion means users opinion. After the extraction of opinion, sentiment classification will be done i.e. whether the expressed opinion is positive or negative. To improve precision or recall of sentiment classification, researchers have worked on aspect extraction [9] [10] [11]. Now aspect based sentiment analyses [12] [13] [14] [15] are very understandable for users, and for companies as well. According to the authors of [16], opinion mining is the attitude of positive and negative opinions. This can be determined by two stages, post and filter processes. Here, the opinionated documents have been ranked in a single process using a special ranking function, opinion tags. Such tags are relating to set of subjective words. Polar vocabulary ambiguity [17] means some of the words have positive polarity in one sense and negative polarity in the other sense. But this problem can be solved with definition and related examples of the word and polarity of the word can be chosen according to the owner of the review/comment or opinion. Due to sheer volume of data through internet, relevant authorities cannot read and understand thousands of reviews in short time. Solution of such issue is the sentiment analysis to determine the actual position of the product/place/reputation from reviews. Next solution is to generate a summary from different features. According to survey [18], different techniques have been used for such issues. According to the proposed methodology of this paper, hyper linked summary can have a huge amount of text but can be read in a few seconds.

Different reviewers express features in different ways, so there is need to determine the candidate features [19]. Such features can be grouped by determining the detailed summary of each word. Proposed methodology is also very useful for such improvements. Due to the vast opinion on the web, summary depiction of such opinion is very important. Results of opinion mining have been summarized by statistical summarization [20].

Tracking over a timeline summarization has been proposed by [5] [21]. The authors divided the task of summarization as a textual, visual, single document based and multi document based approaches [22]. To visualize a summary [23] has used color scheme for product's features assessment. Shaded boxes represent features with different colors to identifying positive, negative and neutral features. Graphical visualization is also very helpful for users' observations, where a bar represents the positive and negative aspects [24].

In all the above fields, major used term is "word/token". Direct opinion, indirect opinion, regular or comparative opinions require different rules on the basis of words. Subjective and objective opinion can be categorized by subjective words. Aspect can be determined by synonym, subjective or objective words. Aspect based sentiment classification can be done through sentiwords etc. In all the above fields, some preprocessing (tokenization + stop word removal + convert lower case, convert into singular, lemmatization etc.), subjective words, objective words and their scores are required to gain the goal; here the authors will provide a strategy/platform from where each and every one may reduce most of the work burden. In this work, given document will be analyzed/summarized with respect to positive, negative, objective and neutral words with their sentiment scores, definitions and examples. Output will be generated in a hyperlinked document; because in such type of documents, summary is very understandable.

2. CREATING SUMMARY OF DOCUMENTS USING WORDS' POLARITY WITH DEFINITION AND EXAMPLES

Proposed methodology will suggest a framework for main pre-processing work, suitable for all types of researches. The proposed method will determine the summaries of given documents containing lists of positive, negative and neutral words with scores as shown in following figure.

Figure-1: Proposed Framework

From above figure, system architecture consists of four stages.

2.1. Dataset preparation

Data in the form of Text can be taken from anywhere related to any domain. System will provide a container in the form of a folder on hard disk. Just place all the documents whose summary is required. These documents can be taken from News, Books or from internet. Here user reviews, sports, politics and medicine domain documents have been summarized to check the maturity of the proposed system about domain independency.

2.2. Filtration of Words

For said words' filtration, system architecture will determine sentiment scores of each word i.e. positive score (PSCORE), negative score (NSCORE) and objective score (OBJSCORE).

Positive Words: PSCORE > NSCORE

Negative Words: NSCORE > PSCORE

Objective Words: PSCORE = NSCORE = 0

Neutral Words: (PSCORE= NSCORE and PSCORE <> 0 and NSCORE<>0)

2.3. Extracting summary elements

Chunks of words from tokenized package of NLTK will be passed through pos tag of NLTK to determine the tags of all words/token. NLTK get_Stop_Words will be used to filter the stop words from filtered words. Now Wordnet dictionary will be used to determine the definition and examples of words.

2.4. Updating output file

System architecture will provide a container, containing the summaries of all the given documents. Although summaries can be generated using text files or excel files, but our aim is to produce a detailed summary with respect to different dimensions. Summary generated in such files is efficient with respect to theory but not efficient with respect to quick reading and understandability. Due to this authentic reason, system architecture will generate summaries of all the files as web files i.e. html or htm files. Where through hyperlinks, summary of required word can be read on the spot by a single click, and can be returned to original stage of summary. The web browser package is used to create a web based document in python [25]. I will use such package to generate output file where summary of the given document will be highly understandable.

3. ALGORITHM OF PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

To achieve the objective of the methodology, work will be categorized into different modules as shown in the following table.

Table-1: Algorithm of proposed work

Input: Text File

List of Positive Words (PW)

List of Negative Words (NW)

Output: HTML File Containing Hyper Links on +ve and -ve Words with Meaning and Examples

Function TextDocumentSummary(Text File)

- 1- WordTokens=Token (Text File)
- 2- **PositiveWords=getPositiveWords(WordTokens)**
- 3- **NegativeWords=getNegativeWords(WordTokens)**
- 4- PositiveWordsDefinition =getPositiveWordsDefinition (**PositiveWords**)
- 5- NegativeWordsDefinition =getNegativeWordsDefinition(**NegativeWords**)
- 6- PositiveWordsExamples =getPositiveWordsExamples(**PositiveWords**)
- 7- NegativeWordsExamples =getNegativeWordsExamples (**NegativeWords**)
- 8- setHTMLFilePW(**PositiveWords**, PositiveWordsDefinition, PositiveWordsExamples)
- 9- setHTMLFileNW(**NegativeWords**, NegativeWordsDefinition, NegativeWordsExamples)

Function Token(Document)

Using word_tokenize of NLTK

Return (Chunks of Document)

End Function

Function getPositiveWords (WordTokens)

For w in WordTokens

 If w is found in Positive_Word Then

 Append w in PositiveWordList

Return PositiveWordList

End Function

Function getNegativeWords (WordTokens)

```
For w in WordTokens
  If w is found in Negative_Word Then
    Append w in NegativeWordList
Return NegativeWordList
```

End Function

Function getPositiveWordsDefinition(PositiveWords)

```
Using synsets dictionary of wordnet
For w in PositiveWords
  If w is found in wordnet.synsets Then
    Append w.definition() in PositiveWordMeaningList
Return PositiveWordMeaningList
```

End Function

Function getNegativeWordsDefinition(NegativeWords)

```
Using synsets dictionary of wordnet
For w in NegativeWords
  If w is found in wordnet.synsets Then
    Append w.definition() in NegativeWordMeaningList
Return NegativeWordMeaningList
```

End Function

Function getPositiveWordsExamples(PositiveWords)

```
Using synsets dictionary of wordnet
For w in PositiveWords
  If w is found in wordnet.synsets Then
    Append w.examples() in PositiveWordMeaningList
Return PositiveWordExamplesList
```

End Function

Function getNegativeWordsExamples(NegativeWords)

```
Using synsets dictionary of wordnet
For w in PositiveWords
  If w is found in wordnet.synsets Then
    Append w.examples() in NegativeWordMeaningList
Return NegativeWordExamplesList
```

End Function

Function setHTMLFilePW(PositiveWords, PositiveWordsMeaning, PositiveWordsExamples)

```
Using webbrowser package
Create an html file which will have all text of input file and hyperlinks on positive words. These links will be redirected to towards summary (Definition and examples) of those words
```

End Function

Function setHTMLFileNW(NegativeWords, NegativeWordsMeaning, NegativeWordsExamples)

```
Using webbrowser package
Update same html file which will have all text of input file and hyperlinks on negative words. These links will be redirected to towards summary (Definition and examples) of those words
```

End Function

4. EXAMPLE BASED ON PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Here, a text file considering an example will be passed through different modules using the proposed work.

4.1. Input module

User will copy the text from any file and paste it in notepad file as shown in Fig-2. This text may be taken from web, through twitter, blogs or online document etc.

Figure-2: Input container

1.1. Token module

This module will return the chunks of whole text (entered from notepad file) as shown in Fig-3.

Figure-3: Chunks of given text

4.2. getPositiveWords and getNegativeWords modules

This module will extract all positive and negative words as shown in Fig-4 and Fig-5.

Figure-4: Extracting positive words

Figure-5: Extracting negative words

4.3. *getPositiveWordsDefinition* and *getNegativeWordsDefinition*

This module will find the definition of extracted positive and negative words as shown in Fig-6 and Fig-7.

Figure-6: Extracting definitions of positive words

Figure-7: Extracting definitions of negative words

4.4. *getPositiveWordsExamples* and *getNegativeWordsExamples*

This module will find the Examples of extracted positive and negative words as shown in Fig-8 and Fig-9.

Figure-8: Extracting examples of positive words

Figure-9: Extracting examples of negative words

4.5. setHTMLFile modules

These modules will automatically generate hyper linked file with summary of each word. Summary will contain positive, negative, objective and neutral words. Scores, identified entity, aspects, and features will be also included in summary. At the end, the finally concluded summary will also be added automatically. Here in Fig-10, a little summary is added. In this figure on the dotted lines there are all words' definitions and examples which have been eliminated due to short space.

Figure10: Summary of given document as html file

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Here, implemented methodology has been applied on user reviews (sentences written by user as review on product or place), medicine domain, politics domain and sports domain. In following table, we are showing the results of ten documents of medicine domain.

Table-2: Analysis of Medicine's Documents

Documents	File Name	Total Words	Extracted Words' Definitions		Extracted Words' Examples	
Document-1	1.txt	36	31	86.11%	24	66.67%
Document-2	10.txt	46	42	91.3%	22	47.83%
Document-3	11.txt	5	3	60.0%	2	40.0%
Document-4	2.txt	33	31	93.94%	16	48.48%
Document-5	3.txt	18	17	94.44%	13	72.22%
Document-6	4.txt	14	11	78.57%	5	35.71%
Document-7	5.txt	46	42	91.3%	22	47.83%
Document-8	6.txt	50	47	94.0%	31	62.0%
Document-9	7.txt	38	36	94.74%	21	55.26%
Document-10	8.txt	30	27	90.0%	14	46.67%

Description of used variables in Table-3 are:

MaxEDW= Maximum Extracted Definition of Words

MinEDW= Minimum Extracted Definition of Words

AEDW= Average Extracted Definition of Words

Table-3: Concluded Results w.r.t. Definitions of Words

Domain		MaxEDE	MinEDW	AEDW	
Hotel Reviews	Users' Reviews	97%	76%	85%	75%
Q-Mobile Reviews		84%	42%	65%	
Medicine		94%	60%	87%	
Politics		97%	85%	92%	
Sports		99%	89%	92%	

From above table, it is clear that the extraction of words' definitions is very acceptable from medicine, politics and sports domains. From users' reviews there is 75% due to misspelled and self-created words by users as shown in Fig-11.

Figure-11: Extracted definition of words in different domains

Description of used variables in Table-4 are:

MaxEEW= Maximum Extracted Examples of Words

MinEEW= Minimum Extracted Examples of Words

AEEW= Average Extracted Examples of Words

Table-4: Concluded Results w.r.t Examples of Words

Domain		MaxEEW	MinEEW	AEEW	
Hotel Reviews	Users' Reviews	71%	42%	54%	44%
Q-Mobile Reviews		61%	20%	34%	
Medicine		72%	35%	52%	
Politics		88%	51%	65%	
Sports		65%	51%	58%	

From above table, it is clear that the extraction of words' examples is above 50%, which are acceptable from domain medicine, politics and sports. From users' reviews, there is 44% due to the misspelled and self-created words by users as shown in Fig-12.

Figure-12: Extracted examples of words in different domains

The aim of this work is to develop a system that will analyze the given document to generate a summary, based on words orientation. Following are the major objectives of the proposed work:

- This work will remove the burden of pre-processing.
- Researcher can generally check whether the given document has opinion or not.
- Lists of positive, negative, objective and neutral words of given document will be generated, which are very useful for different researches.
- Output file as hyper linked document is very useful for quick reading.
- Due to such file, user can take summary of each word on a single click.
- Such type of files can be easily hosted, and users from anywhere can access such files.

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